

Título	Autor	Ano	Base	Status	Motivo	Comentários
The Effectiveness of Serious Puzzle Games on Improving Introductory Learning of Computational Thinking Skills	Christopher Elroy Chandra and Jason Timothy and Dimas Ramdhan	2025	Science@Direct	Aprovado		"No entanto, quando se trata de promover habilidades de Pensamento Computacional, nossas descobertas se mostraram inconclusivas, apesar de termos observado uma tendência positiva nesse sentido."
The effect of simulation games on the learning of computational problem solving	Chen-Chung Liu and Yuan-Bang Cheng and Chia-Wen Huang	2011	Science@Direct	Aprovado		
Evaluating Aspects of Usability in Video Game-Based Programming Learning Platforms	Jaime Díaz and Jeferson Arango López and Samuel Sepúlveda and Gabriel Mauricio (Ramírez Villegas) and Danay Ahumada and Fernando Moreira	2021	Science@Direct	Reprovado	C11	Não tem jogo proposto, apenas aborda plataformas gamificadas.
Code hunt: searching for secret code for fun	Tillmann, Nikolai and Bishop, Judith and Horspool, Nigel and Perelman, Daniel and Xie, Tao	2014	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Sem avaliação, apenas descreve a plataforma + estudo muito curto.
Comparing Block-Based and Text-Based Programming in High School Computer Science Classrooms	Weintrop, David and Wilensky, Uri	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C11	O artigo só compara programação em blocos com a textual.
Applying a Blended Board Game System with Robotic Arm for Training Computational Thinking: Learning through Human-Machine Competition	Yong, Lin and Zhan, Zehui and Zou, Xuanxuan and Chen, Li and Lin, Zhihang and Zhan, Weiyu	2023	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C11	Jogo físico + só ensina pensamento computacional, nada específico de programação.
In-game assessments increase novice programmers' engagement and level completion speed	Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J. and Kwan, Irwin	2013	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		Gidget.
FOES Sparking Programming Interest in Non-IT Students Through a JavaScript Fighting Game	Shaklee, Alex and Burns, Alec and Jin, Wei and Xu, Xin	2023	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Não possui avaliação + estudo muito curto.
Innovate in your program computer class: an approach based on a serious game	Piteira, Martinha and Haddad, Samir R.	2011	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Não possui avaliação, ficou como trabalho futuro.
ENGAGE: A Game-based Learning Environment for Middle School Computational Thinking	Boyer, Kristy and Buffum, Philip Sheridan and Culbertson, Kirby and Frankosky, Megan and Lester, James and Martinez-Arocho, Allison and Min, Wookhee and Mott, Bradford and Rodriguez, Fernando and Wiebe, Eric	2015	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Não possui avaliação + estudo muito curto.
Assembler's Adventure in Sands: A Narrative Puzzle Game for Learning Assembly Logic and Computational Thinking	Leal, Robert Hortua and Imran, Hazra	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Sem avaliação, apenas 5 playertesters.
Design Insights into the Creation and Evaluation of a Computer Science Educational Game	Horn, Britton and Clark, Christopher and Strom, Oskar and Chao, Hilery and Stahl, Amy J. and Hartevelde, Casper and Smith, Gillian	2016	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		Não ensina programação diretamente, ensina o problema de grafos minimum spanning tree.
Towards a new massive multiplayer online role playing game for introductory programming	Malliarakis, Christos and Satratzemi, Maya and Xinogalos, Stelios	2013	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Sem avaliação, apenas proposta do jogo.
Pyrates: Design and Evaluation of a Serious Game Aimed at Introducing Python Programming and Easing the Transition from Blocks	Branthome, Matthieu	2024	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		
Boosting Student Motivation through Game-based Learning in Programming Education with Gamify-IT	Meißner, Niklas and Speth, Sandro and Krieger, Niklas and Becker, Steffen	2026	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		
Optimizing Player Engagement in an Educational Virtual Game through Fuzzy Logic-based Challenge Adaptation	Krouska, Akrivi and Troussas, Christos and Voutos, Yorghos and Mylonas, Phivos and Sgouropoulou, Cleo	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	Artigo focado em aplicar <i>fuzzy logic</i> em um jogo sério já existente.
Revolutionizing C++ Programming Education: A Gamified Interactive Educational Game	Nguyen, Dung	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		
Enhancing Confidence in Using Computational Thinking Skills via Playing a Serious Game: A Case Study to Increase Motivation in Learning Computer Programming	Kazimoglu, Cagin	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		
Evaluating Learner's Usability Using Codenite Educational Battle Royal Programming Language Game	Nobnop, Ratchanon and Tongpaeng, Yoothapong and Thammapalo, Narongrit and Rittidech, Chayangkun and Wira, Marcel and Thawonmas, Ruck	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		

Using an Online Serious Game to Teach Basic Programming Concepts and Facilitate Gameful Experiences for High School Students	Montes, Hernán and Hijón-Neira, Raquel and Pérez-Marin, Diana and Montes, Sergio	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		
Discovering Programming Talent and Improving Learning Motivation with CodeCombat in K-12 Education	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		O artigo avalia o jogo sério "CodeCombat".
Investigating the role of purposeful goals on novices' engagement in a programming game	Lee, Michael J. and Ko, Amy J.	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		Gidget.
ARCode: Augmented Reality Application for Learning Elementary Computer Programming	Sittiyuno, Sirawit and Chaipah, Kornchawal	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado	C11	Não é exatamente um jogo, é uma experiência em RA com gamificação.
Research through Design of Meta-Integrated Programming Educational Games: Uncovering Mechanisms via LDA Topic Modeling	Guo, Shuai and Liu, Da-Wei and Zhai, Chang	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	O Estudo propõe um jogo, mas nenhum tipo de avaliação é feita.
Developing an educational programming game for children with ADHD	Galeos, Christos and Karpouzis, Kostas and Tsatiris, George	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado	C13	O Estudo propõe um jogo, mas nenhum tipo de avaliação é feita.
Using educational games in learning introductory programming: A pilot study on students' perceptions	Ibrahim, Roslina and Semarak, Jalan and Lumpur, Kuala and Jaafar, Azizah	2010	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado	C11	Estudo piloto. Possui avaliação com alunos utilizando 5 jogos, mas não entra em detalhes sobre os jogos.
Teste de Usabilidade: Perspectivas Futuras da Experiência de Meninas em um Jogo de Lógica de Programação	Kenia Reis and Ângelo Feitosa and José Santos Junior and Matheus Araújo and Simone Aquino and Varley Sa	2025	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Reprovado	C13	O artigo foca em fazer teste de usabilidade do protótipo do jogo, além disso a avaliação foram feitas com docentes de computação.
Hello Food: um jogo para praticar conceitos de algoritmos para iniciantes na computação	Jeniffer Macena and Fernanda Pires and Marcela Pessoa and Rafaela Melo	2022	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		O jogo proposto não foi testado com o público-alvo da ferramenta, sendo feito com estudantes e egressos de computação que já possuíam conhecimento prévio.
Uso da Taxonomia de Bloom Revisada em um Jogo de RPG Educacional sobre Conceitos Introdutórios de Programação	Rayssa Santana and Claudia Rizzi and Clodis Boscarioni	2025	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		O artigo propõe um jogo, mas só testa ele com docentes de computação para validar se o jogo está adequado a ser testado com o público alvo, deixando o teste com alunos para trabalhos futuros.
RobotCode: um jogo educacional para auxiliar na aprendizagem de lógica de programação	Fabrizio Honda and Rafaela Melo and Fernanda Pires and Marcela Pessoa	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Reprovado	C13	O estudo é muito curto (2 páginas) e só apresenta o protótipo do jogo, sem testes com usuários.
Um jogo para o ensino de programação em Python baseado na taxonomia de Bloom	Pasqueline Scaico and Diego Marques and Leandro Melo and Max Azevedo and Sinval Neto and Anderson Oliveira and Josinaldo Alves Júnior and Marcelo Labanca and Alexandre Scaico	2012	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Reprovado	C13	O jogo proposto não foi testado com estudantes e não possui nenhum tipo de avaliação. Além disso, parece que o jogo não está finalizado ainda, sendo apenas um MVP / Protótipo.
CODE_DUNGEON: um serious game para auxiliar no aprendizado de programação	Gabriel Oliveira and Elisa Boff	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		
A Serious game for programming in higher education	Thomas Hainey and Gavin Baxter	2024	Science@Direct	Reprovado	CI	O estudo é uma revisão sistemática + proposta de jogo, mas sem algum tipo de avaliação.
Learning Programming at the Computational Thinking Level via Digital Game-Play	Cagin Kazimoglu and Mary Kiernan and Liz Bacon and Lachlan MacKinnon	2012	Science@Direct	Aprovado		Avaliação é feita com voluntários que já possuem experiência com os conteúdos abordados.
The design and evaluation of an AR-based serious game to teach programming	Vandit Sharma and Kaushal Kumar Bhagat and Huai-Hsuan Huang and Nian-Shing Chen	2022	Science@Direct	Aprovado		Reflexão: Jogos de RV e RA fazem parte do meu escopo?
A Serious Game for Developing Computational Thinking and Learning Introductory Computer Programming	Cagin Kazimoglu and Mary Kiernan and Liz Bacon and Lachlan MacKinnon	2012	Science@Direct	Aprovado		
Does text-based programming improve K-12 students' CT skills? Evidence from a meta-analysis and synthesis of qualitative data in educational contexts	Lihui Sun and Liang Zhou	2023	Science@Direct	Reprovado	C14	Não é estudo primário.
Tangibles vs. Mouse in Educational Programming Games: Influences on Enjoyment and Self-Beliefs	Melcer, Edward F. and Hollis, Victoria and Isbister, Katherine	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado	C11	Estudo fora do escopo.

Noisruicer: A Student-developed Game for Recursion	Bakken, Nora and Gonzales, Geoffrey and Jim{e}nez, Osvaldo	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Avaliação planejada, mas não executada.
Progression Trajectory-Based Student Modeling for Novice Block-Based Programming	Morshed Fahid, Fahmid and Tian, Xiaoyi and Emerson, Andrew and B. Wiggins, Joseph and Bounajim, Dolly and Smith, Andy and Wiebe, Eric and Mott, Bradford and Elizabeth Boyer, Kristy and Lester, James	2021	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	O estudo é sobre programação em blocos, não necessariamente sobre uso de jogos.
MoonBase VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game	Holder, Raymond and Carey, Mark and Walder, Patrick and Keir, Paul	2023	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			VR.
ScriptAR: No-Code Development of Augmented Reality Educational Games	Holford, Robert and Wales, Michaelah and Kelly, Lindsey J. and Bednarski, Steven and Bullock, Alison and Harrap, Robin and MacDonald, Zack and Graham, T.C. Nicholas	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	O estudo está fora do escopo desejado.
TeachVR: An Immersive Virtual Reality Framework for Computational Thinking Based on Student Preferences	Wee, Chyanna and Wang, Lillian Yee Kiaw and Ong, Huey Fang	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	É framework, não jogo.
Machineers: playfully introducing programming to children	Lode, Henrike and Franchi, Giuseppe E. and Frederiksen, Niels G.	2013	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Não é um jogo.
The Effects of Adaptive Procedural Levels on Engagement and Performance in an Educational Programming Game	Jemmali, Chaima and Seif El-Nasr, Magy and Cooper, Seth	2022	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Investigating the Interaction of Game Features and Spatial Skills with Performance and Perceived Difficulty in a Block-Based 3D Programming Puzzle Game	Rajapaksha, Yasitha and Thomas Bacher, John and Barnes, Tiffany	2026	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
How can a social debugging game effectively teach computer programming concepts?	Lee, Michael J.	2013	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C14	Gidget. Não é um estudo primário.
Using Commutative Assessments to Compare Conceptual Understanding in Blocks-based and Text-based Programs	Weintrop, David and Wilensky, Uri	2015	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Não é jogo, apenas programação em blocos.
Designing Workshops to Bridge Visual and Textual Programming: A Narrative Game Approach	Matutat, Andr{e} and Franke, Benjamin and Schumann, Niklas and George, Birgit Christina and Keuntje, J{o}rg Michael and Gips, Carsten	2026	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Auto-generated game levels increase novice programmers' engagement	Lee, Michael J.	2020	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			Gidget.
Computational thinking in educational activities: an evaluation of the educational game light-bot	Gouws, Lindsey Ann and Bradshaw, Karen and Wentworth, Peter	2013	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Não há nenhum tipo de avaliação.
Integrating parson's programming puzzles into a game-based mobile learning application	Oyelere, Solomon Sunday and Suhonen, Jarkko and Laine, Teemu H.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	A avaliação ficou como trabalho futuro.
Teaching Foundational Programming to Young Learners via a Block Based Game	Gallacher, Marc and Imperatore, Gennaro	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
(Re)engaging novice online learners in an educational programming game	Lee, Michael J.	2020	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		CE5	Artigo duplicado.
Dragon architect: open design problems for guided learning in a creative computational thinking sandbox game	Bauer, Aaron and Butler, Eric and Popovi{c}, Zoran	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C14	Não é estudo primário.
TurtleTalk: An Educational Programming Game for Children with Voice User Interface	Jung, Hyunhoon and Kim, Hee Jae and So, Seongeun and Kim, Jinjoong and Oh, Changhoon	2019	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			Avaliação apenas com 8 crianças.
Sorting the Universe: Learning Success and Perception of Flow in an Immersive Game for Training Sorting Algorithms	Unro, Daniel and Dengel, Andreas	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
Robot on! a serious game for improving programming comprehension	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2016	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Avaliação ficou para trabalhos futuros.
Exploring the Impact of CodeCombat Python Programming Curriculum on Student Motivation at Primary School	Choi, Iek Chong and Choi, Wan Chong and Chang, Chi In	2025	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Experience with Dream Coders: developing a 2D RPG for teaching introductory programming concepts	Chang, Jack Keng-Wei and Dang, Long Hoang and Pavleas, Jebediah and McCarthy, Joseph F. and Sung, Kelvin and Bay, Jason	2012	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Nenhuma avaliação realizada, apenas proposta do jogo.
Game of Codes: Towards Learning Java by an Educational Mobile Game Adapted to Female Programming Novices	Eiband, Brian Jannik and Bergande, Bianca and Schedel, Angela and Brune, Philipp	2019	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.

Educational game design: an empirical study of the effects of narrative	Jemmali, Chaima and Bunian, Sara and Mambretti, Andrea and El-Nasr, Magy Seif	2018	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		
The Influence of CodeCombat on Computational Thinking in Python Programming Learning at Primary School	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		CE5 Estudo duplicado.
Students' Debugging Behavior Analysis in Game-Based Learning	Yang, Fan and Dong, Zhenghong and Wu, Zhongwang	2021	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11 Foco em ML.
CodeAdventure: Learning Introductory Programming	Nicou, Giorgos and Andreou, Panayiotis and Polycarpou, Irene	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
Using game design mechanics as metaphors to enhance learning of introductory programming concepts	Jemmali, Chaima and Kleinman, Erica and Bunian, Sara and Almeda, Mia Victoria and Rowe, Elizabeth and El-Nasr, Magy Seif	2019	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Sem avaliação.
Program Wars v.2.0 : Improving a Game-based Learning Approach for Teaching Fundamental Programming Concepts	Tareque, Md. Hasan and Deutekom, Steven and Anvik, John and Bashir, Maimoona	2024	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		
Enhancing Informatics Education Through a Serious Game: Design, Development, and Pedagogical Impact	Gkini, Evgenia and Tsaousis, Panagiotis and Sgouropoulou, Cleo and Voyiatzis, Ioannis	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Avaliação ficou para trabalhos futuros.
Accessibility Education for Software Engineers: Evaluating the Impact of Game-Based Learning	Parthasarathy, P D and Joshi, Swaroop	2026	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C12 Focado em acessibilidade digital e o público alvo são engenheiros de software, não iniciantes.
Bug-e-echa 2.0: An Educational Game for CS1 Students and Instructors	Joseph, Amrit M and Sarma, Soumyadeep and Shelly and Kumar, Viraj	2023	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Sem dados de avaliação.
Learning from Teachers: AI-Driven Feedback for a High School Python Serious Game	Branth{ome, Matthieu and Lall{e}, S{e}bastien	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11 Focado em ML.
Codeseum: Learning Introductory Programming Concepts through Virtual Reality Puzzles	Ekman, Johan and Solsona, Jordi and Quintero, Luis	2024	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado		
Impact of Adaptive Feedback on Learning Programming with a Serious Game in High Schools' Classes	Branth{ome, Matthieu and Lall{e}, S{e}bastien	2025	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11 Estudo focado em fazer a transição de alunos com experiência em programação em blocos para a programação em python
A Game-Changing Instructor Tool to Reinforce Coding Concepts	Kletenik, Deborah and Sturm, Deborah	2020	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Artigo muito curto + sem avaliação da ferramenta.
Testando a Diversão em um Jogo Sério para o Aprendizado Introdutório de Programação	Adilson Vahldick and António Mendes and Maria Marcelino and Maciel Hogenn and Pablo Schoeffel	2015	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		
Avaliação da Aplicação de Jogos no Ensino de Programação: Uma Experiência Em Uma Disciplina Introdutória	Paulo Renato Mendes and Pedro Vinicius Freitas and Kássio Romulo Sousa and Carlos Soares Neto	2018	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		O artigo não proee um jogo, mas aplica 6 jogos educacionais com alunos e os avaliam.
Project Éden: platform for introductory programming concepts	Yure Oliveira and Claudio Toledo and Leonardo Pereira	2021	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		
Extracting Learning Analytics from Lightbot Gameplay Sessions	Adriano Gil and Thiago Figueira and José Netto	2024	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado		Artigo muito focado no método de avaliação e extração do desempenho dos alunos.
Gamifying Python: Enhancing Learning Outcomes and Motivation through a Game-Based Approach	Sirikong, Nicha and Visutsak, Porawat	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		
Goos-Gambit: An Educational Card Game	Raikwar, Kanishka and Sheth, Aryan and Shrivastava, Navya and Shete, Prassanna	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C13 Não possui algumtipo de avaliação do jogo, apenas deescreve o processo de desenvolvimnto.
NoBug's Snack Bar: A Computational Thinking Serious Game as an Educational Platform	Vahldick, Adilson and Farah, Paulo Roberto and Marcelino, Maria José and Mendes, António José Nunes	2019	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		
An interactive serious game via visualization of real life scenarios to learn programming concepts	Sajana A. and Bijlani, Kamal and Jayakrishnan, R.	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado		

Creating and Using Digital Educational Games in Adult Education: A Case Study in a Second Chance School in Greece	Karamerou, Vasiliki and Vergados, Dimitrios J. and Vergados, Dimitrios D.	2025	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Não é sobre ensino de programação.
Code Saga – A Mobile Serious Game For Learning Programming	Tacouri, Heeya and Nagowah, Leckraj	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			Avaliação feita com número limitado de alunos.
Investigating the Effect of the Serious Game CodeCombat on Cognitive Load in Python Programming Education	Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Wan Chong and Choi, Iek Chong	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			O artigo avalia o jogo sério "CodeCombat".
Integrating Serious Game in Personalized Learning Environment	Wee, Vivian Gek-Ting and Chua, Fang-Fang	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	O artigo é sobre a sistema de aprendizado.
Visual Learning on Mobile Phone for Introduction Basic Programming in Vocational High School	Kurniawati, Arik and Akbar, Nurrohmat Hidayatullah and Prasetyo, Deny	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			
Programming Education for Young People using the Falling-Puzzle Game, "Puyo Puyo"	Saito, Daisuke and Tian, Ruochen and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Ensino através do Scratch, não é um jogo em si.
Gidget: An online debugging game for learning and engagement in computing education	Lee, Michael J.	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	O artigo apenas propõe o jogo + estudo muito curto. Gidget.
Mining Learners' Behavioral Sequential Patterns in a Blockly Visual Programming Educational Game	Shih, Wen-Chung	2017	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	O artigo apenas propõe como fazer a avaliação sem executa-la + estudo muito curto.
Pyrus: Designing A Collaborative Programming Game to Promote Problem Solving Behaviors	Shi, Joshua and Shah, Armaan and Hedman, Garrett and O'Rourke, Eleanor	2019	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	O jogo não é para o ensino de programação
Teaching Object Oriented Programming Concepts Through a Mobile Serious Game	Lotfi, Elaachak and Mohammed, Bouhorma	2018	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Foco no ensino de POO + não possui forma de avaliação.
C++ Adventure: A Mixed Methods Pilot Study on Digital Game-Based Learning of Coding and Effect on Motivation	Cu Hao, Lester and Delantar, Ma. Buena and Tan, Giselle Jasmine	2021	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Integrating Learning Analytics in an Educational MMORPG for Computer Programming	Malliarakis, Christos and Satratzemi, Maya and Xinogalos, Stelios	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C12	O artigo apresenta um jogo educacional, mas é focado em aplicar análise de aprendizagem nesse jogo.
Using a Serious Game Approach to Teach 'Operator Precedence' to Introductory Programming Students	Adamo-Villani, Nicoletta and Haley-Hermiz, Thomas and Cutler, Robb	2013	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			Focado em regras de precedência dos operadores.
Programming Games as Learning Tools: Using Empathic Design Principles for Engaging Experiences	Maxim, Raluca Ionela and Arnedo-Moreno, Joan	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			O estudo avalia 5 jogos existentes, mas está avaliação é focada em Design Empático.
Programming Education Through Game-Based Learning and Quizzes	Bubenkova, Lenka and Pietrikova, Emilia	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Não tem um jogo proposto, apenas aplica aprendizagem baseada em jogos com questionários.
Poké Prog: Jogo educacional para o ensino dos conceitos básicos de programação	Jeanluca Abreu and Hugo Castro and Clausius Reis and Pedro Sousa	2023	SBC-OpenLib (SOL)	Aprovado			
Design and Development of Learn Your Way Out: A Gamified Content for Basic Java Computer Programming	Nerico L. Mingoc and Erik Louwe R. Sala	2019	Science@Direct	Reprovado		C11	O artigo apresenta um conteúdo gamificado para ensino de Java, não é um jogo em si.
Mobile Escape Rooms for Learning Programming in Nigerian Higher Institutions	Chinedu Ugo, Chidera	2024	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C13	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
Bug-eecha: A Gamified Approach to Programming Problem Comprehension and Testing	Kumar, Viraj and Joseph, Amrit M. and Sarma, Soumyadeep and Shelly	2023	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		CE4	Não está disponível
Teaching Programming with Gamified Semantics	Arawjo, Ian and Wang, Cheng-Yao and Myers, Andrew C. and Andersen, Erik and Guimbretièr, Françoise	2017	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Não é jogo, apenas gamificação
Exploring an approach based on digital games for teaching programming concepts to young children	Tancicleide Carina {Simões Gomes} and Taciana {Pontual Falcão} and Patrícia {Cabral de Azevedo Restelli Tedesco}	2018	Science@Direct	Reprovado		C11	Não tem jogo em si, apenas abordagens gamificadas.

A blocks-based serious game to support introductory computer programming in undergraduate education	Adilson Vahldick and Paulo Roberto Farah and Maria José Marcelino and António José Mendes	2020	Science@Direct	Aprovado			
Office Madness: Investigating the impact of a game using a real life job and programming scenario on player experience and perceived short-term learning	Stelios Xinogalos and Savvas Eleftheriadis	2023	Science@Direct	Aprovado			
A comparative analysis of programming games, looking through the lens of an instructional design model and a game attributes taxonomy	Lieve Laporte and Bieke Zaman	2018	Science@Direct	Reprovado		Cl3	Comparação de vários jogos, mas sem avaliação.
Programming Fun(damentals): Using commercial video games to teach basic coding to adult learners	Joan Arnedo-Moreno and David García-Solórzano	2025	Science@Direct	Aprovado			Avalia 2 jogos comerciais de programação.
Games for Coding to Attract New Students to STEM	Calvo-Morata, Antonio and Humble, Niklas and Mozelius, Peter and Pechuel, Rasmus and Fernández-Manjón, Baltasar	2024	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Nenhuma avaliação realizada.
Learner Attitude, Educational Background, and Gender Influence on Knowledge Gain in a Serious Games-Enhanced Programming Course	Zhao, Dan and Muntean, Cristina Hava and Chis, Adriana E. and Muntean, Gabriel-Miro	2021	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			
Evaluating the quality of games designed for learning programming by students with different educational background: An empirical study	Orehovački, Tihomir and Babić, Snježana	2015	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			
Serious games for motivating into programming	Hijon-Neira, Raquel and Velázquez-Iturbide, Ángel and Pizarro-Romero, Celeste and Carriço, Luís	2014	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado			
Empowering Education through EERP: A Customizable Educational VR Escape Room Platform	Darejeh, Ali	2023	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
Cross platform interactive programming learning environment for kids with edutainment and gamification	Sarkar, Shubhra Prakash and Sarker, Biplab and Hossain, S.K. Alamgir	2016	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Sem avaliação.
Exploring Game Elements in Learning Programming: An Empirical Evaluation	Santos, Adriano Lages dos and Souza, Maurício R. de A. and Dayrell, Marcella and Figueiredo, Eduardo	2018	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			
An experimental evaluation of scaffolded educational games design for programming	Jantan, Siti Robaya and Aljunid, Syed Ahmad	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			
Serious games for learning programming languages	Mitamura, Tamotsu and Suzuki, Yasuhiro and Oohori, Takahumi	2012	IEEE Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Sem avaliação.
GidgetML: An Adaptive Serious Game for Enhancing First Year Programming Labs	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2020	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			Gidget.
PlayLOGO 3D: A 3D Interactive Video Game for Early Programming Education: Let LOGO Be a Game	Paliokas, Ioannis and Arapidis, Christos and Mpimpitsos, Michail	2011	IEEE Digital Library	Aprovado			Avaliação com especialistas, baseadas em heurísticas de usabilidade.
A TUI-based Programming Tool for Children	Wang, Danli and Zhang, Lan and Qi, Yunfeng and Sun, Fang	2015	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl1	
Enhancing Programming Education through Game-Based Learning: Design and Implementation of a Puyo Puyo-Inspired Teaching Tool	Tian, Ruochen and Saito, Daisuke and Washizaki, Hironori and Fukazawa, Yoshiaki and Kobayashi, Hiroshi and Tsuji, Ayumi	2024	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Estudo muito curto + sem avaliação.
The computational puzzle design framework: a design guide for games teaching computational thinking	Jiang, Xina and Hartevelde, Casper and Huang, Xinyuan and Fung, Anthony Y. H.	2019	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl3	Apresenta apenas a proposta, sem avaliação.
RoboBUG: A Serious Game for Learning Debugging Techniques	Miljanovic, Michael A. and Bradbury, Jeremy S.	2017	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Software visualisation through video games	Marques, Bradley R. C. and Levitt, Stephen P. and Nixon, Ken J.	2012	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
If Memory Serves: Towards Designing and Evaluating a Game for Teaching Pointers to Undergraduate Students	McGill, Monica M. and Johnson, Chris and Atlas, James and Bouchard, Durell and Messom, Chris and Pollock, Ian and Scott, Michael James	2018	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		Cl1	Propõe um framework, mas a avaliação fica para trabalhos futuros.

Evaluation of the user experience and intrinsic motivation with educational and mainstream digital games	de Lima, Luis Gustavo Rotoly and de Lima Salgado, Andr{e} and Freire, Andr{e} Pimenta	2015	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		C11	Jogos não são de programação introdutória.
Intrinsic vs. Extrinsic Programming Challenges in Educational Games: How they shape Children's Computational Thinking, Learning Drive, and Game Engagement	Chen, Baijun and Pan, Yushan and Xiang, Nan and Huang, Shenze Shandel	2026	ACM Digital Library	Aprovado			
Serious game development as a creative learning experience: lessons learnt	Garneli, Varvara and Giannakos, Michail N. and Choriantopoulos, Konstantinos and Jaccheri, Letizia	2015	ACM Digital Library	Reprovado		CE4	Estudo não disponível.